

**Deliverable D-JRP-
PARADISE-WP4.1**
**Report on the cloning and
sequencing of aptamers
specific for *C. parvum* and
*G. duodenalis***

**Workpackage 4 of
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE**

Responsible Partners: P27-ISS, P11-
RKI, P1-ANSES, P41-SVA

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	Deliverable D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.1
Project Acronym	JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE
Authors	Marco Lalle (ISS); Gregory Karadjan (ANSES); Simone M. Cacciò (ISS); Christian Klotz (RKI); Karin Troell (SVA).
Other contributors	PARADISE consortium
Due month of the report	M36
Actual submission month	M45
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: September 8, 2021
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s): The European Union Reference Laboratory for Parasites and the National EU Reference Laboratories for Parasites</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>

D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.1

REPORT ON THE CLONING AND SEQUENCING OF APTAMERS SPECIFIC FOR *C. PARVUM* AND *G. DUODENALIS*

BACKGROUND

This is a public deliverable of One Health EJP Joint Research Project:

JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE – *PARASite Detection, ISolation and Evaluation*

(<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-paradise/>);

Work Package:

JRP- PARADISE –WP4 Parasite enrichment strategies;

Task:

JRP-PARADISE-PARADISE-WP4-T1 Development of pre-DNA extraction enrichment strategies.

Project Leader: Simone M. Cacciò, ISS; Deputy Project Leader: Karin Troell, SVA.

WP Leader: Marco Lalle, ISS; Deputy WP Leader: Karin Troell, SVA.

Task Leader: Christian Klotz, RKI; Deputy Task Leader: Gregory Karadjian, ANSES.

Contacts: Simone M. Cacciò, simone.caccio@iss.it; Marco Lalle, marco.lalle@iss.it;

PARADISE WP4 aims to improve the performance of current approaches to detect *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* (oo)cyst contamination in food, through the development of parasite enrichment strategies, which should improve the sensitivity of detection and deliver less expensive methods applicable to food matrices.

The objectives of PARADISE WP4 are:

- ✓ To develop two pre-DNA extraction enrichment protocols based on two alternative affinity reagents, nanobodies (single-chain variable fragment antibodies) and aptamers (oligonucleotides that bind to a specific target molecule);
- ✓ To assess nanobodies and aptamers application for magnetic capture of *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* (oo)cysts in different matrices;

- ✓ To develop a protocol for post-DNA enrichment to concentrate parasite DNA based on hybridization of target-specific biotinylated probes.
- ✓ To evaluate pre- and post-DNA extraction enrichment strategies by inter-laboratory comparison

This deliverable reports on part of the first objective of PARADISE WP4, i.e., the screening and selection of highly affine and specific aptamers with the ability of binding *C. parvum* or *G. duodenalis* (oo)cyst for pre-DNA extraction enrichment strategy.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Cell-SELEX experimental design

Aptamers are single stranded (ss) oligonucleotides (RNA or ssDNA) that can fold into functional spatial structures and therefore can allow binding to a target (such as molecules or cells) with high affinity and high selectivity. Aptamers have been identified able to bind to either parasite molecules or whole organism (Tonelli et al., 2013; Ospina-Villa et al., 2020; Niederlender et al., 2021), and can be used to develop diagnostic tests. Aptamers have the advantage to be easy and cheap to synthesize in comparison to antibodies, and are more suitable to be applied for cost-effective diagnostics. Aptamers are identified starting from a library containing a random pool of billions oligonucleotides by several *in vitro* rounds of an iterative process of evolutionary selection that exponentially reduced sequence complexity.

Two partners institutes, ANSES and ISS, were in charge of the experimental work to identify aptamers against *Giardia duodenalis* cysts and *Cryptosporidium spp.* oocysts. Based on relevant literature (i.e. Iqbal et al., 2015) and previous expertise at ANSES (Niederlender et al., 2021), a strategy focusing on ssDNA-aptamer was chosen to perform Cell-SELEX (Systematic Evolution of Ligands by EXponential enrichment) assay. Indeed, ssDNA is more chemically and biologically stable than RNA, making both selection and application easier. A detailed Cell-SELEX protocol was developed following Iqbal et al., 2015.

The starting ssDNA library consisted of synthetic 80 mer oligonucleotides (10^{14} – 10^{16} sequences) with a randomized region of 40 nucleotides (N40) flanked by two constant primer-hybridization sites for the amplification. The iterative process of SELEX involves several rounds of positive selection consisting of the following steps: i) incubation of the ssDNA library with target (*Giardia* cysts or *Cryptosporidium* oocysts); ii) discharge of unbound ssDNA from target; iii) recovery of bound ssDNA from target by heat denaturation; iv) amplification and fluorescent-labelling of ssDNA by symmetric and asymmetric PCR; v) purification of ssDNA (aptamers pool) from PCR primers and buffer, vi) monitoring of ssDNA by agarose gel electrophoresis and quantification by UV spectrophotometer. A total of 10 rounds of SELEX were planned.

The use of consecutive DNA amplification by symmetric PCR followed by asymmetric PCR was selected as a cheap and straightforward strategy to prepare high amount of ssDNA. By the use of an unequal molar ratio of forward and reverse primers, the asymmetric PCR preferentially amplifies one strand of the parental DNA as PCR proceeds. Double stranded DNA as well as free primer sequences are then removed by size-exclusion centrifugal devices.

To increase the selection of specific aptamers, a negative selection step against a non-target organism (e.g. *Cryptosporidium* oocyst for *Giardia* SELEX and *Giardia* cyst for *Cryptosporidium*-SELEX) was added from SELEX cycle 3 to 8 before the amplification step.

Moreover, to increase for highly affine aptamers, a progressive decrease in (oo)cysts amount and interaction time at each round was undertaken during the first step. To ensure that the selected aptamers would bind to (oo)cysts present in field samples, target-ssDNA incubation was always performed in solution, using unfixed and not-immobilized (oo)cysts not older than 3 months from their preparation.

A study visit, planned at the beginning of the project (April 2020) and aiming to ensure knowledge transfer of the Cell-SELEX technology from ANSES to ISS was cancelled due to the restriction imposed by Covid-19 pandemics. The scope of the study visit was partly accomplished by several online meetings between the two partners. However due the uncertain evolution of the restrictions caused by the Covid-19 pandemic and limited access to laboratory, to ensure the timely deliverable of the expected results without altering the original workplan, the more experienced partner institute (ANSES) performed individual cell-SELEX for both parasites, whereas the other partner (ISS) focused only on *G. duodenalis*.

Progress in the experimental work at both partner institutes was heavily affected by continuous stop-and-go due to national lockdowns and delays in the supply of reagents. Cell-SELEX experimental work started in May-June 2020 and was completed between December-February 2021.

Experiments were performed using the following materials:

- i. a synthetic single-stranded (ss) DNA library consisting of a randomized region of 40 nucleotides (N40) flanked by two constant primer-hybridization sites;
- ii. cysts of *Giardia duodenalis* isolate WBC6 (Assemblage A), produced at ISS by *in vitro* encystation of cultured trophozoites;
- iii. cysts of *Giardia duodenalis* isolate H3 (assemblage B), purified from faeces of *in vivo* experimentally infected gerbils, were purchased from an international provider;
- iv. oocyst of *Cryptosporidium parvum* IOWA strain, purified from faeces of *in vivo* experimentally infected calves, were purchased from an international provider;
- v. oocyst of *Toxoplasma gondii* Savannah isolate (genotype II), purified from faeces of *in vivo* experimentally infected cats, were provided by the TOXOSOURCES project (Prof. B. Koudela, VRI);

Target-ssDNA incubation and positive selection (as well as negative selection) were performed using different amount of (oo)cysts and different incubation time with aptamer pools at each SELEX cycle

***Cryptosporidium*- and *Giardia*-SELEX at ANSES**

Five experimental replicates for both *Cryptosporidium*-SELEX and *Giardia*-SELEX were performed using as targets oocyst of *Cryptosporidium parvum* IOWA strain and cysts of *Giardia duodenalis* isolate H3, respectively. For the negative selection, *Giardia* cyst were used in *Cryptosporidium* SELEX and *Cryptosporidium* oocysts in *Giardia* SELEX. For each parasite and replicate, ten SELEX round were performed, following the protocol described above. To monitor progress in aptamers selection, an indirect measurements approach was used to assess reduction in sequence diversity of the pools. A SYBR green-qPCR

with melting curve (MCA-qPCR) analysis assay (Luo et al., 2017) was performed every 5 SELEX rounds. Higher is the oligonucleotide pool complexity faster and more pronounced is a fluorescence drop in the amplification curve with a melting curve showing a major peak at lower temperature. With the decrease of pool complexity, fluorescence drop disappear and peak at higher temperature are evident in the melting curve. Therefore, the changes in amplification curves and melting curve directly correspond to aptamer species convergence as SELEX proceeds. Indeed, a significant increase in melting peak from cycles 5-6 and an even more pronounced increase at cycle 10 were observed for all *Cryptosporidium*- and *Giardia*-SELEX replicates. However, identification of enriched aptamers by conventional cloning and sequencing of amplified products was not possible. Indeed, a remarkable range of diversity (constituted by 1N to 20N on the 80 bp aptamer sequences) could not be reached, even at round 10, suggesting the presence of a high amount of random and non-specific oligonucleotides. Moreover, we observed a relevant amount of PCR by-products starting from approximately round 5 or 6.

To overcome this limitation, aptamers pools from round 10 were analysed by an NGS approach as detailed below.

Giardia-SELEX at ISS

In a first experiment, three experimental replicates for *Giardia*-SELEX were performed, using either Assemblage A or Assemblage B cysts, and *Cryptosporidium* oocysts for negative selection. For each parasite and replicate, eight SELEX rounds were performed, following the protocol described above. To monitor progress in aptamers selection, MCA-qPCR was used in combination with qualitative evaluation of aptamer binding to *Giardia* cysts by fluorescence microscopy (FM). For FM, *Giardia* cysts were incubated with fluorescent-labeled aptamer pool or, as control, fluorescent-labeled ssDNA library. In MCA-qPCR, a significant increase in melting peak from round 5 was observed, although FM assay did not show any difference in fluorescent labelling of cysts incubated with the ssDNA library or the aptamer pools. Moreover a prevalent amplification toward PCR by-products of large size was observed.

Based on the unsatisfactory results obtained, and data from a recent publication (Sefah et al., 2010), the cell-SELEX protocol was substantially revised. The most relevant modifications included:

- To limit the production of undesired PCR by-products, only symmetrical PCR was used,
- Preparation of sense ssDNA relies on biotinylation of PCR products and affinity purification (Sefah et al., 2010; Wilson, 2012).
- Negative selection was performed with *T. gondii* oocysts

With the new protocol, a total of 12 cell-SELEX rounds were performed in triplicate. A slight increase in the melting curve peak was observed up to round 10, and remained stable in the following rounds. This is suggestive of a decrease in pool complexity. To identify potentially enriched aptamers, samples from all SELEX rounds for each pool were subjected to NGS analysis and compared with the ssDNA library (see below)

High-Throughput Sequencing (HTS) of aptamers

Cloning and Sanger sequencing has been commonly used to sequence aptamers pool of the last SELEX round and identify the few predominantly amplified sequences. However, this low throughput approach is limited to approximately 100 clones, thus strongly limiting sequences retrieval. High-Throughput Sequencing

(HTS) has been recently used as an alternative approach. HTS has the advantage to provide not only much more sequence information, by returning thousand of sequences at once, but also to allow monitoring of sequences enrichment along the whole SELEX process by comparing sequencing data obtained from each round. Thus, this approach consents to identify relevant sequences even when they do not represent the most abundant. Appropriate algorithms to handle and analyse the large amount of sequencing data are necessary (Nguyen Quang et al., 2016).

The aptamers pools of the last three rounds of *Cryptosporidium*- and *Giardia*-SELEX from ANSES and aptamers pools from all rounds of *Giardia*-SELEX from ISS were then subjected to HTS by an Illumina® platform. Data analysis by sequence clustering using the most abundant sequences as 'seeds' was performed with a dedicated workflow.

Comparison of sequence clustering between the replicates allows the identification for each SELEX project of 20 highly enriched sequences (or sequence families) Most of these sequences have Guanine-rich motifs, Notheworthy, no overlap could be observed between aptamer sequences obtained from *Giardia*-SELEX at ANSES and ISS or with *Cryptosporidium*-SELEX. This might reflect the different protocols applied, but could also suggest target specificity of the aptamers.

Future work

The synthesis of all the selected aptamers (with appropriate molecular tags) is ongoing, although delays might be expected due to the G-rich composition of the sequences. Different assays will be applied to test the ability of aptamers to bind the appropriate target, to measure the binding affinity, to evaluate the eventual effect of different tags and strategies for coupling to magnetic beads (e.g. FM, ELISA, FACS, SPR). The most appropriate protocols are under revision. Aptamers will be tested with the different technologies at the two partner institutes (ANSES and ISS) will provide cross-check validation.

References

- Iqbal A, Labib M, Muharemagic D, Sattar S, Dixon BR, Berezovski MV. Detection of *Cryptosporidium parvum* Oocysts on Fresh Produce Using DNA Aptamers. PLoS One. 2015 Sep 3;10(9):e0137455. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0137455. PMID: 26334529; PMCID: PMC4559477.
- Niederlender S, Fontaine JJ, Karadjian G. Potential applications of aptamers in veterinary science. Vet Res. 2021 Jun 2;52(1):79. doi: 10.1186/s13567-021-00948-4. PMID: 34078451; PMCID: PMC8172000.
- Ospina-Villa JD, Cisneros-Sarabia A, Sánchez-Jiménez MM, Marchat LA. Current Advances in the Development of Diagnostic Tests based on Aptamers in Parasitology: A Systematic Review. Pharmaceutics. 2020 Oct 31;12(11):1046. doi: 10.3390/pharmaceutics12111046. PMID: 33142793; PMCID: PMC7693570.
- Luo Z, He L, Wang J, Fang X, Zhang L. Developing a combined strategy for monitoring the progress of aptamer selection. Analyst. 2017 Aug 21;142(17):3136-3139. doi: 10.1039/c7an01131h. PMID: 28792025.

- Sefah K, Shangguan D, Xiong X, O'Donoghue MB, Tan W. Development of DNA aptamers using Cell-SELEX. *Nat Protoc.* 2010 Jun;5(6):1169-85. doi: 10.1038/nprot.2010.66. Epub 2010 Jun 3. PMID: 20539292.
- Wilson R. Preparation of single-stranded DNA from PCR products with streptavidin magnetic beads. *Nucleic Acid Ther.* 2011 Dec;21(6):437-40. doi: 10.1089/nat.2011.0322. Epub 2011 Nov 2. Erratum in: *Nucleic Acid Ther.* 2012 Apr;22(2):137. PMID: 22047177.
- Nguyen Quang N, Perret G, Ducongé F. Applications of High-Throughput Sequencing for In Vitro Selection and Characterization of Aptamers. *Pharmaceuticals (Basel).* 2016 Dec 10;9(4):76. doi: 10.3390/ph9040076. PMID: 27973417; PMCID: PMC5198051.
-